

**New best results
for some known instances of the
Permutation Flow-Shop Problem (PFSP)
v. 10e**

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Abstract

This report presents solutions that, as of the date of publication, improve the cost (makespan) for 52 instances of the Permutation Flow-Shop Problem (PFSP) proposed by Eric Taillard or by Eva Vallada, Rubén Ruiz, and Jose M. Framinan. This report may help those who assess the quality of heuristics based on their ability to approach the best-known solutions. Three algorithmic techniques used are also presented: the super-prohibition sieve excluding paths with weights exceeding a given bound, the adaptive compartmental neighborhood with selective 2-closing, and finally the makespan calculation performed using upper-windowed multi-numbers.

Résumé

Ce rapport présente des solutions améliorant, à date de publication, le coût (makespan) pour 52 instances du problème du Flow-Shop de permutation (PFSP) proposées par Eric Taillard ou par Eva Vallada, Rubén Ruiz et Jose M. Framinan. Ce rapport peut aider ceux qui évaluent la qualité d'une heuristique selon sa capacité à s'approcher des meilleures solutions trouvées. Trois techniques algorithmiques utilisées sont également présentées : la super-interdiction des chemins de poids supérieurs à une borne, le voisinage à compartiment adaptatif en 2-fermeture sélective, et enfin le makespan calculé en multi-nombre fenêtré haut.

Report

The Permutation Flow-Shop Problem (PFSP), with minimization of the makespan criterion (often denoted C_{\max}), is a well-known optimization problem. It is NP-Hard for a number of machines greater than or equal to 3 (Garey et al., [1]).

Two datasets are very often cited in this context:

- the 120 instances that Eric Taillard proposed in 1993 (ref. [4]),
- the 480 instances that Eva Vallada, Rubén Ruiz and Jose M. Framinan proposed ([6]).

In both cases, 10 different problems are given for each configuration of P jobs \times M machines.

When a problem is prefixed by "Ta" in this context, we know it is one of the instances proposed by Taillard. Respectively, the "VFR" (sometimes VRF) refer to problems submitted by members of the University of Valencia (Spain).

Since these instances were proposed, they have allowed to:

- energize the field by proposing a kind of "high-score panel" to the many researchers working on this subject.
- validate the quality of heuristics, or parts of heuristics.

Indeed, finding a "new best solution" to one or more Ta or VFR problems is generally perceived as a performance.

Moreover, we often compare the "distance to the best solution found" (in percentage) that a heuristic manages to reach in (P x M x 45ms) execution time on a "regular" computer.

This metric disqualifies any non-constructive heuristic, which is why we do not use it.

Nevertheless, since the emergence of metrics based on known instances, both (1) the best solutions found, (2) implementation qualities (3) programming language performance and (4) CPU speeds have varied greatly, which may have placed some against others on an inequality ratio of 1 to 500.

At a time when we propose to compare the performances of quantum and non-quantum computers according to metrics based on NP-Hard problems (Atos, [10]), and where the question of the algorithm used by each arises, work exploiting "classical" supercomputers has made it possible to propose new best solutions and also to demonstrate the optimality of certain solutions (Jan Gmys, [7] and [8]).

This report presents 52 new "best solutions", as of the publication date. The improvement can reach 1.89% compared to the reference dataset made available in 2021 (Jan Gmys, [9]).

Some doors are closed to independent researchers.

*arXiv and HAL are for example inaccessible.
The Zenodo platform is fortunately more tolerant.*

Making numerical solutions available first should allow to date "useful by themselves" results and open other outlets for sharing methodological information.

Regarding the reproducibility of the results:

Strict reproducibility of results obtained by such a complex algorithm requires distributing either an executable and/or the source code. However, the security context precludes the distribution of opaque executables.

Reproducibility is illusory in a domain where atypical computer hardware is sometimes used. Moreover, even when this is not the case but executions cannot be carried out to completion, it may yield better solutions for those who simply have a bit more time or resources. Yet, the best solutions must continue to reward those who advance the methods.

Reproducibility is therefore not an objective currently being pursued.

Those who had put online the solution collections [5], [9] and [13] have been notified, so that their repositories can remain up to date.

I sometimes keep them informed of successive discoveries in real time, and I would like to apologize for this.

Test Campaign

When heuristics are iterative, or when they do not really have an "end of processing", we would sometimes like a "much longer" trial to be described, on one or more sizing instances. Indeed, good "long-term" convergence, without imposing systematic achievement of the global optimum, is a heuristic quality at least as important as initial convergence speed (often measured by the ARPD at MxPx45ms).

This "ultimate attempt" is here the main activity: improving the best known solution.

The calculation is therefore prolonged long enough, generally at least one day after the last improvement found. Moreover, this "additional" delay is not frozen: it can for example be extended if quite long inter-improvement delays have been encountered before. It is mainly about stopping, but without missing improvements close to a new solution.

The objective pursued, as well as the limited material and human resources (a single operator using two PCs costing less than 800 euros and without a GPU), mean that the tests cover only the still open problem instances, involving up to 100 jobs.

Presented in three sentences, this heuristic, which I have modestly called "BRunner" (for "bound-runner"), is a non-stochastic local search of maximum slope descent type with super-tabu list with "bound" parameter, quasi-stack exploration depth-first and neighborhood extension by nested, coroutine-based exploration of places.

Tabu methods have been described by Fred W. Glover ([2]).

Our list consists of "super-forbidden" permutations.

The super-prohibition of a permutation (called "central permutation") amputates the space of permutations of a set of size much greater than 1: its cardinality grows rapidly with the makespan of the "central" permutation. The large size of the "super-forbidden" "zone" that is added to the tabu list at each move of the local search contributes enormously to improving convergence. By adding a denominator growing with the complexity of the problem, the super-prohibition could even make believe, in first analysis, that it is possible to contain the combinatorial explosion of the space of permutations when (P, M) increases and therefore the complexity of problems.

But these first positive impressions are nevertheless largely tempered afterwards by enclave problems (of the solution and/or of the traversal cursor) and the presence of an intrinsic aspiration criterion, inherent to the fact that the super-forbidden spaces located around two central permutations belonging to the tabu list, partially overlap (without the central permutations being able to be covered).

A counter-directional pre-processing, not counted in the indicated processing times because optional and negligible in proportion, aims to start the search on a permutation maximizing "as much as possible" the makespan.

This "Ready player one" start is not a whim of a charlatan claiming to be able to start his algorithm from anywhere. On the contrary, we first climb towards the summits because we noticed, without having yet been able to precisely quantify the phenomenon, that such a start often led "more quickly" towards "lower" regions. Like the hero of Ernest Cline's novel, we then have the impression of finding a shortcut.

An early and rather modest paper by the present author (which was in fact his last one, and is cited here mainly for historical completeness and because the co-author first introduced the PFSP problem to him during a DEA course) addresses this opposite search ([18]).

The techniques currently used are entirely different from those described in that paper — which is polynomial, indeed linear, only with respect to the number of jobs — but, 30 years later, that paper still appears to be the only one to have addressed this topic.

We do not know if these better results (necessarily in the end, since we start from much higher) are due to additional wandering allowed before a bias definitively diverts the algorithm from the global optimum, or if they result from an unexplained subliminal phenomenon, for example subtle guidance during the "easy" phase of initial descent.

The location reached after an unimpeded steepest-descent move from the highest makespan during the first iterations resembles the solutions produced by constructive heuristics. Our initial approach avoided both external method outputs and restarts from dataset best-found solutions.

Might we allow ourselves to start from a solution provided by a constructive heuristic in order to avoid the non-trivial preliminary step of searching for the highest makespan? The quick answer to this question is probably no, because we see in it a form of "free lunch" ([19]) from a more "meta" perspective.

Indeed, the Kendall tau distance plots, introduced in version 10, show alignments that can be detected within the very first seconds (sometimes with two alternatives and a heuristic that switches from one to the other). On the contrary, it seems crucial to start from this worst solution if one wants to exploit a trajectory. The aim is to design more predictive heuristics, steering the search by exploiting vanishing lines, grooves of improvement, and these cannot be satisfied with a starting point located "anywhere".

The Alps do not necessarily share their characteristics with Mont Blanc (their highest peak). But in the PFSP, the initial descent very likely provides information about the whole surrounding space, and it seems essential to exploit everything that can be exploited if we are ever to obtain heuristics, or even algorithms, that are truly more effective (We could push the metaphor further by mentioning runs that alternate between the Maurienne and Tarentaise valleys, but that would make the report a bit too locally flavored).

In the meantime, our multi-number computations, which discriminate between permutations with equal scalar makespan values, could no doubt be of benefit to certain existing constructive heuristics (an issue already addressed in [17] for the NEH heuristic [16]) and might also lead to new ones.

These unsubstantiated indications are nevertheless stated because it is clear that, for lack of time, this research cannot be carried out here.

Base 1 data are occasionally manipulated, to increase the discrimination of the makespan criterion (tie management using secondary objectives from a graduated scale of minimal relaxations), which could limit the complexity hope to pseudo-polynomiality, but this is done in an optimized way and less/not sensitive to the values of the delay matrix.

The whole is implemented in C++ and x64-AVX2 and AVX512 assembly language.

The multi-threaded executable is run on an Intel Core i5-14600K or AMD Ryzen 9 9900X CPU, using no more than a third of their capacity: the goal is not to push them further in order to keep the liquid cooling system silent on PCs that are also used for algorithm development and other projects.

The implemented multithreading approach introduces specialized (yet reassignable) auxiliary threads alongside a main thread, which also serves as both an active and passive orchestrator:

- It acts actively when initiating a super-tabu screening computation under a collaborative paradigm, operating on an extensive list of super-tabu permutations distributed across collision-computation threads (“C” threads).
- It acts passively when defining central permutations whose neighborhoods must be evaluated, a task handled by neighborhood-computation threads (“V” threads) according to a work-stealing paradigm.

The indicated times are not final: both the implementation and the algorithmic aspects are being constantly reworked. As is always the case with work in progress, apart from better solutions, it is not really possible to publish anything definitive.

From version 5 of this report, a data collection ("dataset"), composed of 3 CSV files, is shared at the address <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16328984> . This will be updated at the same time as this report (same version names).

These files were initially taken from Jan Gmys's repository (ref. [9]). They now have:

- an identical structure (for the 3 files),
- a numerical column entitled "UBFoundBy":
 - "0" indicates a pre-existing result from [9].
 - "50" indicates a pre-existing result from [13].
 - "100" (simple neighborhood) or "101" (adaptive neighborhood) indicates that the best solution originates from the present work.

Besides the fact that it is desirable to remember who found what, the history of obtaining each result also has technical importance, especially when trying to understand why a new heuristic improves certain instances better than others. Some teams do not treat all instances, or do not treat them in the same way.

Additions in version 8

A version 8 of the report and the dataset are put online to reflect the fact that the work on multi-threading and the AVX512 port has indeed been completed.

There are also a few new results found during testing, without any real systematic approach:

- A solution at 6357 for Ta088 improves the solution at 6367 mentioned in version 1.
- A solution at 6016 for VFR100_20_8 improves 6020 previously mentioned.

On January 11, 2026, I discovered that a team had posted an preprint (in [11] that became [12]) referencing results that had been available since July 7, 2025 ([13]).

This team did not take into account the results from Jan Gmys's team, nor obviously mine (my report was only at version 3 at that time, in French, and with results only at the end of the text as here).

No matter, these results improve 90 of VFR instances with Jobs ≥ 200 et $M \geq 40$.

I merged these new data into my CSV files, assigning the index "50" to the results from this source.

In dataset [13], there are also improvements to results that I had posted online, therefore for instances with number of jobs ≤ 100 .

8 solutions are concerned, including 7 for which I yield precedence as long as I don't find anything better:

- VFR50_15_10 and VFR50_20_1 (same makespan, different solutions, I was two days late)
- VFR50_20_8 (same makespan, same solution, I was also two days late)
- VFR60_20_6 (same makespan, same solution, mine was first online)
- VFR50_20_3, VFR60_20_5, VFR100_60_5 and VFR100_60_9 (better makespans found by the other team)

As a result, the 49 improvements of report version 7 become 42 improvements in version 8.

To try to understand what happened, I started re-running the multi-threaded version of the heuristic on these 8 instances that were counted in the "49 improvements" of version 7 of this report.

Some runs were undoubtedly cut too short after an improvement was found compared to the previously known results.

Example : VFR50_20_3.

3773 had been reached in 44 seconds in single-thread mode on a laptop (based on an Intel Core i7-1360P) slower than the usual test machine of the time (based on an Intel 14600K), and this run had been stopped after 2h30. The instance seemed "easy" and the computation appeared to have reached its end.

In the report (v4), a rule of three had transformed the time to obtain it into "30 seconds".

The current multi-threaded version, executed on the second test PC based on AMD 9900X, in a 6-thread configuration (to stay within the L3 cache of a single DIE, and also to allow another run simultaneously), reaches 3773 in 20 seconds (identical trace).

The stage reached in 2h30 on the laptop is now achieved in 30 minutes.

The acceleration ratio, which was 5 with the laptop, is only 3 with single-threaded executions on the desktop test PCs. Indeed, the two multi-threading techniques implemented (collaboration for collision/super-prohibition calculations and "work-stealing" for neighborhood makespan calculations) mean that the gain materializes gradually. Additionally, threads are reassigned from one activity to another as the tabu list grows.

Finally, the solution at 3772 indicated in is reached after 38 minutes and 55 seconds. After that, nothing more for at least 4 days and 2 hours, the time when this report is put into translation and then online.

Additions in version 9

Version 9 of the report and dataset has been published online, including new best-known solutions for certain instances among the 8 previously overtaken by source 50 (ref. [13], January discovery) over the present work (Index 100).

Although the implementation improved certain runtimes — thereby accessing harder-to-reach solutions — the bulk of the progress stemmed from a neighborhood change. The neighborhoods employed are detailed in the final section of this report.

To better assess the respective contributions of the two implemented changes, two runs were systematically performed for each instance:

- a first "baseline" run on 6 threads, benefiting solely from the implementation speedup (multi-threading and AVX-512 vs. AVX2),
- a second run using the alternative neighborhood, also on 6 threads and thus benefiting equally from the implementation speedup.

Runtimes for the "baseline" runs are comparable to those reported in versions 1–7 of this report.

The two new runs are directly comparable: they differ only in neighborhood structure and execute concurrently on the same PC (AMD Ryzen 9 9900X with 12 Zen 5 cores). Results from the new neighborhood carry source index "101" in the dataset.

SMT multi-threading (2 threads per core) is not used due to performance slowdowns observed in our case. Thread affinity is thus configured such that each 6-thread run utilizes a single 6-core DIE (with its dedicated 32 MB L3 cache), with one thread per physical core. No data prefetching is performed to compensate for cache tabu list overflow: although possible and conceptually defined, optimizations that manifest so late are not a priority in an experimental project.

Things are more nuanced, and version 10 revisits these two points: the use of SMT multithreading and cache overflow caused by the tabu list.

Instance	Previous runs NBH-11 (v1-v7)	Dataset [13] (50)	New runs: 6-thread multi-threading & AVX-512			
			« As-is » run NBH-11 (100)		NBH-15 neighborhood (Index 101)	
	Best Makespan (total run)	Best MS	Time to previous MS	Best MS (total run time)	Time to previous MS	Best MS (total run time)
VFR50_15_10	3396 : 1min39s (12h)	3396		3396 : 44s (2h30min)	3396 : 11min43s	3394 : 15min57s (27h13min)
VFR50_20_1	3677 : 10min (3h laptop)	3677		3677 : 3min23s (31h30min)		3677 : 3min36s (31h30min)
VFR50_20_3	3773 : 30s (2h30 laptop)	3772	3773 : 20s	3772 : 38min55s (100h)	3773 : 10min45s	3772 : 47min42s (100h)
VFR50_20_8	3771 : 19min8s (4h10min)	3771	(*)	3771 : 2h19min (25h20min)	3771 : 10min35s (*)	3770 : 29min22s (25h10min)
VFR60_20_5	4174 : 22min6s (25h)	4173		4174 : 5min39s (70h)	(4175 : 38min9s) 4175 → 4172	4172 : 18h12min (94h35min)
VFR60_20_6	4173 : 1h33min (30h30min)	4173		4173 : 23min9s (18h)	(4176 : 4min2s) 4176 → 4173	4173 : 4h (13h)
VFR100_60_5	9376 : 5h1min (48h)	9369	9376 : 1h7min	9375 : 36h20min (132h)	9376 : 45min3s 9366 : 1h10min	9345 : 57h41min (132h51min)
VFR100_60_9	9450 : 115h (163h36min)	9445		9450 : 23h8min (202h)	9450 : 1h52min 9443 : 2h6min	9416 : 178h30mi (202h)

(*) Modified initial scheduling (vs. prior runs): the maximum makespan has been increased.

The "Time to previous makespans" columns may report passage times to lower values when those makespans were not encountered first.

These calculations improve results and regain 5 out of the 7 lost instances.

The new runs are faster overall, with the alternative neighborhood consistently outperforming the original — despite occasional temporary lags (typically on low-machine instances). However, these specific cases, flagged by another heuristic as less effectively handled with the original neighborhood, do not permit firm conclusions. Most often, improvements with the original neighborhood cease entirely well above the stabilization level achieved by the new one.

This striking discontinuity retrospectively validates early run terminations (no further gains possible) while exceeding expectations for neighborhood extension NBH-11→NBH-15 benefits alone. It points to underlying inefficiencies elsewhere — partially mitigated by the new neighborhood: excessive forward progress neglecting lateral exploration, and underutilization of the highly connected multi-dimensional search space.

The heuristic already integrates a mechanism for extending its basic neighborhood, which was expected to yield greater efficiency.

This mechanism can be compared to the algorithmic operations (chaining, mixing, etc.) that one might apply to a “basic” random number generator in order to enhance its characteristics and produce a stream tailored to the consumer of randomness (e.g., multidimensional uniformity).

The logical extension of the basic neighborhood did not perform as well as the explicit extension.

Improvements are being considered, and progress is possible in many parts of this heuristic.

What to make of seemingly endless experiments — overly laborious perhaps?

What to do with results obtained so late?

- a benchmark solution collection for heuristic positioning,
- a way to go with limited resources, but with more than $P \times M \times 40ms$.

While runs yielding improvements after 178h may appear impractical, they reduce the UB by 0.3% following a 115h→1h52min compression, while excelling at shorter durations. Long-run archives remain indispensable for convergence analysis, where order-of-magnitude gains occasionally emerge. Progress logging — despite slowing execution and generating up to 700 MB traces — is currently unavoidable.

These new results eclipsing prior ones serve as a reminder that many teams have incrementally advanced these datasets over time. Properly documenting the employed techniques offers the sole fitting homage — advancing the global research endeavor.

Relative heuristic stabilization — coupled with modest visibility from online releases garnering hundreds of views — was required to avert plagiarism risks.

Before recomputing the results for all instances, a few open VFR instances that had not been improved during the first round of experiments were retested as a priority. The goal was to quickly return to 49 improvements, but the count eventually reached 50.

While maximizing improved instances matters, runs extend beyond early gains to preclude revisits.

What about the Intel 14600K-based PC?

With only 6 effective high-performance cores (the other 8 being non-comparable), it is used solely for single 6-thread runs. Even with AVX2 (AVX-512 unavailable), run starts remain very fast while the tabu list is small and makespan calculations dominate. This stems from Intel's faster indirect memory access vector instruction (vpgatherdd, used to reorder the delay matrix according to schedules in "general" makespan computation). Nevertheless, collision calculations (i.e., super-prohibition tests) are faster on the AMD PC and eventually dominate: they require no gathering and benefit from more vector registers, enabling greater loop unrolling without memory stores. AVX-512 offers little speed advantage over AVX2 for this heuristic, but the extra registers (32 vs 16) make a difference with 20+ machines.

The VFR100_60_9 run with the new neighborhood (see bottom-right former table results) was replicated identically on the 14600K. Leading substantially early on (-30% delays), it still tops milestones 9450 (1h46min) and 9443 (1h59min), but logically falls behind later. Naturally, during this run, the 9900X simultaneously executed another 6-thread run (using the original neighborhood).

The 14600K PC performed the additional computations whose results are presented below.

(This hatched table is included again in Version 10, with improvements)

Instance	Previous runs (unreported)	Dataset [9] Source (0)	New runs: 6-thread multi-threading & AVX2			
			« As-is » run NBH-11 (100)		NBH-15 neighborhood (Index 101)	
			Best MS (total run)	Best MS	Time to previous MS	Best MS (total run)
VFR100_20_1	6121 : 32h (183h)	6121			6120 : 87h16min (*)	6116 : 88h44min (116h)
VFR100_20_3	6163 : 20h (230h)	6157			6161 : 12h31min 6157 : 24h55min	6152 : 30h36min (73h)
VFR100_20_10	6084 : 21h (100h)	6084			6084 : 22h3min	6077 : 26h42min (37h+)

(*) Modified initial scheduling (vs. prior runs): the maximum makespan has been increased.

Additions in version 10

Improvement of best known solutions (BKS):

First, the previous table is updated.

Instance	Previous runs (unreported)	Dataset [9] Source (0)	New runs: 6-thread multi-threading & AVX2			
			« As-is » run NBH-11 (100)		NBH-15 neighborhood (Index 101)	
	Best MS (total run)	Best MS	Time to previous MS	Best MS (total run)	Time to previous MS	Best MS (total run)
VFR100_20_1	6121 : 32h (183h)	6121			6120 : 87h16min (*)	6116 : 88h44min (116h)
VFR100_20_3	6163 : 20h (230h)	6157			6163 : 15h46min 6157 : 21h43min	6147 : 37h45min (206h)
VFR100_20_10	6084 : 21h (100h)	6084			6083 : 30h43min	6075 : 40h (125h)

(*) Modified initial scheduling (vs. prior runs): the maximum makespan has been increased.

The best solutions for VFR100_20_3 and VFR100_20_10 have been improved.

Few instances have been explored since Version 9 of this report was published: only VFR100_20_3, Ta087, and Ta085 were used as test cases for algorithmic modifications.

Recently, **Ta085** and **Ta087** were improved during extended tests, after introducing a modification that allows a normally fixed algorithmic parameter to evolve. These findings prompted the present reposting.

Presentation of a graphing tool:

To add value to the dataset report, this version presents a small graphing tool developed in Python (2,400 lines), and uses the run that improved the BKS of Ta085 as an illustration.

AI tools were used in this development, mainly Claude (Anthropic), but also ChatGPT (OpenAI). These new assistants prove useful when guided by precise prompts and asked for reasonable increments that can be checked.

For users who already have some background knowledge, AI tools greatly expand both knowledge and practical feasibility. They can process a report such as this one without difficulty, and the resulting contextualized dialogues can at least stimulate serendipity. Used as interactive documentation as early as the AVX vectorization stage (with mixed success at the time, due to hallucinations about the instruction set) these investigations have already benefited greatly from such new resources.

They sometimes provide a name, and identify prior references, for techniques used “like Monsieur Jourdain” by researchers who have not read much of the work of others.

While they can sometimes simplify and enhance translations, they also erase peripheral handicaps.

However, the coding of the solver itself has remained entirely human so far.

Below is a graphical representation of the full execution trace. The tool can display up to three traces, either reference traces or traces currently being generated, in a consistent and incremental manner, without rereading everything at each refresh. It can also be run several times side by side.

The best makespan found (in green) and the size of the taboo list (in indigo) can be seen progressing over time. Several variables can be selected for each of the three differently colored series.

At the time of the screenshot, the mouse pointer was positioned on the indigo peak preceding the improvement to 6284 (1d20h8min). The tool indicates that there were then 337,514 super-forbidden permutations in the taboo list.

The makespan scale is shown here in logarithmic mode, and the run can be seen to start above 10,203; its actual initial value is 11,193.

The tool avoids label overlap: it draws labels starting from the end of the run, and refrains from covering the previous label actually drawn.

The vertical scale for taboo-list sizes is linear. The list is reset whenever an improvement is found, and its growth accelerates shortly before some improvements. This corresponds to the discovery of a new basin.

The taboo-list size also increases linearly with time, indicating an efficient implementation: collided elements are moved to the front of the list, and the collision-rank distribution is exploited in two distinct sectors. Its probability density, apparently exponential in shape, is handled differently for very low ranks and for higher ranks.

This is the type of insight expected from such a tool.

The 1% (6347), 0.5% (6316), and 0.25% (6300) zones relative to the previously known BKS (6285) are shown by horizontal lines. The 1% threshold is crossed 34 seconds after the start, the 0.5% threshold after 19 min 33 s, and the 0.25% threshold after 1 h 4 min.

Below, on the left, is a zoom along the x-axis at the beginning of the run, this time using a linear scale for the makespans. The taboo-list size scale has also been zoomed.

The time $M \times P \times 40$ ms is shown as a vertical line for reference.

The BKS value is not updated in real time in the plotter when an improvement occurs. However, these threshold crossings seem more appropriate for characterizing convergence with respect to the state of the art, and therefore including the latest BKS value found.

After restarting the tool, which preserves its configuration between sessions, the display takes the new BKS of 6277 into account (right): 6339 (1% in 83 s), 6308 (0.5% in 6 minutes), and 6292 (0.25% in 2 h 31 min 18 s).

A Kendall-distance diagram ([14]) can be displayed in the upper-right area. It represents the direct line between the initial and final permutations of the run as a horizontal segment AB of fixed length. It then connects the successive intermediate permutations found, i.e. improvements, after positioning them in the plane according to their Kendall distances to the two distinguished permutations A and B.

For this type of representation, it is useful to have “global and fixed” permutations, such as our “worst starting points”, and to start all runs from them.

Other identifiable permutations could be used, for instance those obtained by constructive heuristics. However, they would not always provide the absolute reference made possible here by this “zero”, this “origin” that we seek and from which we start.

Positioning permutations relative to it always gives the overall diagram a reasonably good scale.

Other versions of this diagram, better suited to the relative representation of two runs, can be selected in the tool. The brown color, that starts at the summit pointed to by the arrow added in this report, indicates the portion lying beyond the right edge of the main graphical area at the time this screenshot was captured. This boundary was deliberately set at 6 h 30 min, corresponding to the arrival time at point C of the lower run:

These representations provide information on early divergences, wandering paths, and the relative proximity of the trajectories to the two final permutations.

If two trajectories are already available for two different values of an algorithmic parameter, such as the maximum size of a beam list, they make it possible to create a hybrid run by precisely grafting the parameter change at a given point along one path, where a reversal may, for example, indicate a capacity break.

However, nothing can be inferred

- from the apparent length of the segments. The tetrahedral computation of the point coordinates, which are located according to their Kendall tau distances to A, B and C, acts like an inverted magnifying glass: there is greater accuracy in the vicinity of the three vertices,
- from the apparent “intersections” of the trajectories: the projected space has far more than two dimensions, and a crossing of trajectories in the plane does not mean that there are similar permutations.

The traversal times are not represented either: the visible separation above appears 6 seconds after the start of both runs; afterwards, the upper one reaches B (where the makespan is 6277) after 71 h 34 min, and the lower one reaches C (MS = 6285) after 6 h 30 min.

The solver implementation runs at variable speed depending on the execution configuration, but the path is always identical: work-stealing threads affect only speed. “Natural” randomness does not affect the algorithm’s course, and no “artificial” random-number generator is used.

The illustrated run was performed on the AMD 9900X-based PC, using a 9-thread configuration, detailed later.

This time would no doubt have been increased by at least 25% on the Intel 14600K-based PC. Indeed, a three-hour gap, i.e. -15% for the faster, is already observed when reaching the former BKS value, 6285, on another run and this gain rate would asymptotically increase toward a ceiling of about 30%:

Comparison of two identical runs on two different PCs: the lighter curve corresponds to the Intel 14600K run, and the darker one to “half” an AMD 9900x CPU. The red curves correspond to the number of algorithm iterations. Further improvements occur to the right of the displayed area, but the comparison run was stopped after 23 h.

The start of the run that improved Ta087, on a logarithmic scale for the makespans and with a Kendall tau distance diagram (the point C defining the projection plane comes from another run and is not displayed). The size of the taboo lists is falsely linear due to sampling limited to the start/end points.

The entire run that improved Ta087, on a linear scale for the makespans and with a Spearman footrule ([20]) distance diagram (using the same point C as in the previous figure). We observe that the size of the tabu list evolves in a less linear manner. This is due to the instance (many ties) and, consequently, to the moderate use of a comb technique on a beam list of limited size (it is not possible to present everything in a 35-page report).

Optimization of the execution configuration: Simultaneous Multi-Threading and prefetching

This paragraph addresses less theoretical aspects and will mainly interest readers who wish to know more about our particular solver implementation, designed for a consumer-grade computer, with only six cores used per run.

SMT multithreading is a CPU technology that allows one physical core to execute two threads while giving the appearance of two complete cores. These are called logical cores, since the operating system does not need to switch between the two tasks thus executed - no interrupt, no saving of one execution context, no reloading of the other, etc. - because the processor keeps both active at the same time.

Two logical cores execute their instructions in a much more interleaved manner than two tasks switched by an operating system. There are indeed two complete register sets, avoiding any context saving, and often, though not permanently, there is genuine simultaneous execution of elementary instructions from the two SMT tasks/threads, insofar as modern cores often have “more tools available” than work that can be performed at a given instant. Because of dependencies between instructions within a thread, two execution pipelines from two threads make better use of shared resources - compute units, memory access, etc. - than a single one.

Splitting a given repetitive workload into two SMT tasks therefore always produces the complete result faster than executing it with a single thread.

Remarkably, however, the relative gain increases when memory access becomes slower. In other words, the time loss caused by increasingly frequent accesses to data missing from cache is strongly amortized. Indeed, within an SMT core, each of the two running tasks exploits the additional memory-wait pauses of the other, simply because it then benefits from more resources for a while. For the overall throughput to be maintained, it is enough that the core remains active.

Finally, when two identical tasks are executed with SMT - same code, regular repetition - a temporal offset naturally occurs that optimizes their interleaving, and this also improves overall throughput, by the principle of anti-phase shifting in coupled oscillators.

Thus, splitting each of our threads into two SMT threads proved clearly more efficient when those threads operate on more data than can fit in the processor’s L3 cache, i.e. the threads collaboratively computing collisions with the taboo list.

It practically eliminated both the need for and the usefulness of prefetching list elements, which in any case had not yet been implemented.

Conversely, our work-stealing implementation for computing all makespans in a neighborhood is single-threaded: one thread computes an entire neighborhood. Parallelism only arises through predictive computation of several different neighborhoods in different threads.

Thus, several threads may compute several neighborhoods simultaneously, but the neighborhood awaited by the algorithm at a given time is produced by a single thread. That thread is necessarily penalized when it has an SMT co-tenant on its execution core, especially one performing the same type of computation.

Since this time loss is not sufficiently compensated elsewhere, by a larger number of precomputed neighborhoods being available, we do not use SMT co-location for neighborhood-computation threads. We continue to bind them to distinct cores, without co-tenants.

We therefore tested runs using more than six threads, first on the Core i5-14600K.

No notable change was observed on short runs.

On long runs, execution is faster when increasing from 6 to 9 threads on the six available performance cores. The eight “efficient” cores are about three times slower, so we do not use them and leave residual system activity to them.

This is true provided the threads are distributed as follows:

$$CV - C|C - C|C - C|C - V - V$$

Here, V denotes work-stealing threads computing neighborhoods, and C denotes threads computing the super-forbiddenness sieve for part of the taboo list. “CV” denotes the main thread, which can either compute complete neighborhoods or participate collaboratively in the taboo-list sieve by computing its share.

Note: the configuration “CV - C|C - C|C - C|C - V - V” is the final state reached when the taboo list becomes very large. The initial distribution, and the one restored after each improvement of the best known makespan, is “CV - C|V - C|V - C|V - V - V” while the taboo list remains small, sometimes for several hours on 100-job instances. The implementation progressively reassigns selected threads as the taboo list grows.

A load-balancing mechanism is included for the threads jointly computing the taboo sieve, i.e. the C threads. Whenever no collision is detected, meaning only when computation proceeds to the end of the sublists assigned to each thread, the thread that finishes first is considered the fastest and therefore receives the next additions.

In this way, whether threads run alone or in pairs, on one core or another, on one die or another, the workload automatically balances itself as well as possible. This may be described as result-driven load balancing, a technique disturbed only by strong variations in thread performance. This occurs slightly while C threads are co-located via SMT with V threads, whose activity is random and coarse-grained. But it eventually disappears once the final configuration is active.

Automatic thread balancing produces trace measurements indicating that, in a given period, once the list exceeds 20 times the L3 cache size, a core running two SMT threads performs up to 167% of the work achieved by a single-threaded core. Before that, while the cache is still sufficient, the rate is only 150%.

Single 9-thread runs on the 14600K are then roughly as fast as 6-thread runs on the 9900X: super-forbiddenness computations, much slower on the 14600K (AVX2 versus AVX-512), are then performed by 7 threads instead of 5, while cache misses are compensated.

View of the Performance tab of the Task Manager on the 14600K

(VFR100_20_1: 100 jobs × 20 machines, with 200K elements in the taboo list at the time of capture)

The six physical performance cores are shown in orange.

The average global CPU-activity is about 22% (14% at the exact time of capture), but this includes the efficient cores and a misleading 100% indication for the V threads. These execute an active waiting loop for their next task, including an `_mm_pause()` instruction: 150 clock cycles paused for 3 active cycles, all counted as activity. In reality, only the main thread (CV) is effectively active more than 80% of the time, less than the reported 100% because it often waits for the completion of a neighborhood computation started, but not yet finished, by another V thread. Liquid cooling keeps the temperature at 50–55°C without audible discomfort.

The 12 fast logical cores actually appear to be occupied at about 30% on average.

We then propagated this configuration change to the two runs that can be executed simultaneously on the Ryzen 9 9900X. The gain was also considerable on long runs, and it put the AMD platform clearly back in the lead.

A view of the 9900x with a run on Ta087 (500K in the list) across the 12 low logical cores, and another run on Ta085 (650K in the list) across the 12 high logical cores.

The CPU is then operating at 40% utilization (and 55°C with no noticeable noise).

Algorithmic Methods

This section introduces three novel, reusable techniques integral to the heuristic. Full result reproducibility remains unavailable pending broader dissemination of the algorithmic components.

Caveats: - Formal mathematical treatments are deferred here for descriptive clarity. This document reflects a computer scientist's algorithmic explorations.
- Prior art may exist for presented techniques; relevant citations will be incorporated upon identification.

The literature review focused exclusively on publications and datasets surpassing benchmark solutions. While result improvements were viewed as clear advances, their precise positioning within the field remains to be clarified.

Super-prohibition

Local search algorithms iteratively traverse a problem's solution space, maintaining a current location as a core state component. This may represent: (1) a single solution (e.g., latest PFSP schedule); (2) an explored set (e.g., visited schedules); or (3) a nested subspace with hierarchical locality. Neighborhood operators enable incremental transitions or expansions within this space.

The current location undergoes either displacement (point locations) or expansion (composite locations). Transitions proceed incrementally via algorithmically defined neighborhoods within the solution space.

Tabu search enhances local search by maintaining a tabu list of recent solutions, preventing cycles and enabling escape from local optima through enforced exploration of diverse neighborhoods.

Tabu enforcement on candidate schedules can use hash tables and hash functions for $O(1)$ membership checks, ensuring rapid rejection of revisited solutions.

For large-scale problems, exhaustive tabu lists become infeasible due to combinatorial explosion. To spend less time in a locality, one approach modifies the exclusion criterion to forbid more locations per iteration.

A super-local prohibition is a parameterized sieve defined by a super-prohibited location and applied to a contemplated neighboring solution. This test excludes the super-prohibited location as well as other "nearby" locations sharing characteristics with it.

The additionally prohibited locations have not actually been explored, but what truly matters when prohibiting locations is that:

- their makespan is superior or equal to the best makespan found up to that point,
- their "best" non-included neighborhood be scrutinized in search of better neighbors,
- the locations added in a single batch exhibit a certain convexity (more precisely, a star-shaped set: a union of convex sets all containing the same central location).

This convexity aims to respect locality and avoid creating intrinsic enclaves (i.e., immediate ones due to a single added set). Convexity already implies an implicit neighborhood relation. While multiple neighborhoods can be considered, for the convexity discussed here, we add (and prohibit) sets of complete schedules, including all possible permutations of parts within certain adjacent part groups.

By making more "massive" additions to the prohibited space, even if it takes more than one iteration to examine the best accessible locations from the added super-prohibited sets, one can still obtain a heuristic that converges faster.

The key is to efficiently traverse the added sets by performing a nested local search within them. This aspect of the algorithm will be described later.

In BRunner, the tabu list size is unbounded, but the list resets whenever a better makespan is found.

Runs concluding with 1,500,000 or 2 million elements are common in this report.

Let P be the number of jobs and M the number of machines in a PFSP problem instance.

Let S be a permutation of the P jobs.

A) The matrix view $VMat(S)$ of a schedule S is the $M \times P$ matrix reproducing the processing delays ordered according to S .

We consider the paths in the oriented grid graph connecting cell $VMat(S)_{1,1}$ to cell $VMat(S)_{P,M}$, always progressing either to the adjacent cell in the next column or to the adjacent cell in the next row.

The count of these paths is :
$$\frac{(M+P-2)!}{(M-1)!(P-1)!}$$

The weight of such a path is the sum of $(P+M-1)$ processing times, i.e., the sum of the values of its cells taken from $VMat(S)$.

The makespan $MS(S)$ of a schedule S is the weight of the maximum-weight path in its matrix $VMat(S)$.

The makespan can be computed by constructing an intermediate matrix $MSMat(S)$, which is defined as follows:

- $MSMat(S)$ has the same dimensions as $VMat(S)$
- $MSMat(S)_{1,1} = VMat(S)_{1,1}$
- $\forall m = 2, \dots, M$ $MSMat(S)_{1,m} = MSMat(S)_{1,m-1} + VMat(S)_{1,m}$
- $\forall p = 2, \dots, P$ $MSMat(S)_{p,1} = MSMat(S)_{p-1,1} + Vmat(S)_{p,1}$
- $\forall m = 1, \dots, M$ and $\forall p = 2, \dots, P$
 $MSMat(S)_{p,m} = \text{Max}(MSMat(S)_{p,m-1}, MSMat(S)_{p-1,m}) + Vmat(S)_{p,m}$
- $MS(S) = MSMat(S)_{P,M}$

Multiple grid paths may attain identical weights, including several achieving the critical makespan path $MS(S)$.

The distribution of path counts by weight approximates a Gaussian: few paths reach the makespan, then increasingly more at lower values, finally tapering toward the minimum-weight path.

This is not an immutable property but a general trend—multimodal distributions occur. Crucially, paths with weight \geq limit L surge when L decreases or when switching to higher-makespan schedules (fixed L).

B) The set of schedules super-prohibited by a super-taboo set T is defined as the union of all sets of schedules super-prohibited by each individual schedule in T .

Super-prohibition actually incorporates a numeric threshold parameter L in its definition.

For $S \in T$ and threshold L , the sieve prohibits all S' admitting a common path with S of weight $\geq L$

L is fixed to the best known makespan value at the current stage of the tabu search algorithm.

Recall: The super-taboo list resets upon each best found makespan improvement, such that L cannot evolve without T having been reset. This prevents any unintended and uncontrolled expansion of the super-prohibited space when decreasing L .

C) For a candidate schedule C , a super-taboo schedule S , and numerical limit L , the super-taboo sieve is defined as:

C is super-prohibited by S for L if and only if there exists a common path between C and S of weight $\geq L$

D) Testing every path in S with weight $\geq L$ quickly becomes very time-consuming when S 's makespan is "far above" L . Indeed, the number of paths at a given weight grows rapidly as the critical weight L falls below the makespan value.

Things were actually done this way at one time, which allowed testing the exclusion of critical paths only, or paths carrying along (i.e., compatible with) the most schedules. Enumerating all paths that needed consideration was not trivial.

Additionally, the super-taboo list grows continuously, requiring super-prohibition testing against each of its elements at every step until a global decision can be made.

E) It is possible, in a single computation of complexity equal to that of an isolated makespan calculation (thus in $O(P \times M)$), to determine whether C and S share a common path of weight greater than or equal to L , regardless of L and the makespans of C and S .

A path is said to be common to C and S if and only if, at the positions where this path contains a "horizontal" segment:

1. the corresponding jobs are identical in C and S ;
2. and the set of jobs encountered before that position is identical in both C and S .

The objective is to determine whether there exists a common path whose weight exceeds L .

- ✘ We will not examine all paths of C with a weight greater than L and, for each of them, verify its horizontal segments to check whether S presents the same jobs at those positions (condition 1) and whether condition (2) also holds.
- ✓ Instead, we will define a *fixed/mobile* characteristic for each position of C and S . We will then use this characteristic to compute the maximum weight of the paths common to C and S , and finally compare this maximum weight with L .

A position is said to be *fixed* if the same job appears there in both C and S and, moreover, no job located before that position in C appears after that position in S .

Fixed positions thus act as impassable barriers: one can transform C into S without moving any job from a *fixed* position, and without swapping jobs that are separated by *fixed* positions.

Mobile positions are those that are not fixed.

Mobile positions never occur in isolation: there are always at least two consecutive *mobile* positions. Consecutive *mobile* positions define a *mobile range* within which jobs may be freely rearranged.

Example 1: If $S = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6\}$ and $C_1 = \{2, 1, 3, 4, 5, 6\}$, then all positions are *fixed* except the first two.

Example 2: Conversely, if $C_2 = \{6, 2, 3, 4, 5, 1\}$, then no position satisfies the definition of a *fixed* position.

For two given schedules C and S , the *mobile* positions are the positions where are located jobs that must be "moved or jumped over by another job" when relocating all jobs from their position in C to their position in S . This can be visualized as performing a kind of "minimalist morphing" transforming C into S or S into C .

Fixed positions are those that do not move during this morphing (and are not even jumped over by another job).

As a first approach, we can design an algorithm that considers all positions as fixed initially. Then, for each job numbered p , if its position in C differs from its position in S , all positions between the position of p in C and the position of p in S are made mobile, boundaries included.

This yields a final mobility indication, applicable to both S and C , for all positions.

The paths of $V\text{Mat}(S)$ (or $V\text{Mat}(C)$) whose all horizontal segments are located at "fixed" job positions according to this mobility indication are both paths of $V\text{Mat}(S)$ and $V\text{Mat}(C)$.

F) Determining the "mobile" positions, for two orderings C and S , is actually a task of lower complexity than our first algorithmic approach has suggested. It is achievable in $O(P)$.

The position's mobility depends only on the schedules, not on the delay values.

We can simply traverse C and S in parallel while maintaining a « DéjàVu » array of flags indicating whether a job was met once before.

A position is "mobile" if the job at that position in S is different, or if a job already seen in C (at the same rank or an earlier position) has not yet been seen in S .

This latter condition can be determined by maintaining a global count of the number of jobs "met only once" (so that it is not necessary to re-traverse the DéjàVu flag array).

```

Noted, all indices (arrays and job numbers) are assumed to start at 1.
PositionIsMobile[] is an uninitialized array of P booleans that this code must set

Initialize an array of P booleans DéjàVu[] to False
jobC = C[1]
jobS = S[1]
If jobC = jobS Then
    PositionIsMobile[1] = False
    NbJobsMetOnlyOnce = 0
Else
    PositionIsMobile[1] = True
    NbJobsMetOnlyOnce = 2
    DéjàVu[jobC] = True
    DéjàVu[jobS] = True
End If
For CurrentPos from 2 to P
    jobC = C[CurrentPos]
    jobS = S[CurrentPos]
    If jobC = jobS Then
        If NbJobsMetOnlyOnce = 0 Then
            PositionIsMobile[CurrentPos] = False
        Else
            PositionIsMobile[CurrentPos] = True    → because the position is jumped over
        End If
    Else
        PositionIsMobile[CurrentPos] = True
        If DéjàVu[jobC] Then NbJobsMetOnlyOnce = NbJobsMetOnlyOnce - 1
        Else NbJobsMetOnlyOnce = NbJobsMetOnlyOnce + 1
        If DéjàVu[jobS] Then NbJobsMetOnlyOnce = NbJobsMetOnlyOnce - 1
        Else NbJobsMetOnlyOnce = NbJobsMetOnlyOnce + 1
        DéjàVu[jobC] = True
        DéjàVu[jobS] = True
    End If
End For

PositionIsMobile[] now contains the mobility flag of each rank

```

Once the *mobile* and *fixed* positions are known, we can compute a "compatibility makespan" between C and S. Simply comparing this makespan value to L then yields the sieve result.

G) The procedure for computing the compatibility makespan is very similar to the usual makespan calculation: we proceed line by line from top to bottom, and within each line from left to right, to sequentially compute the cells of a second matrix $MSMat(S)$, of the same form as $VMat(S)$.

The value of each cell in this second matrix is calculated based on the value immediately above it and the one immediately to its left :

$$MSMat(S)_{p,m} = \max(MSMat(S)_{p-1,m} , MSMat(S)_{p,m-1}) + VMat(S)_{p,m}$$

The only nuance is that, for "mobile" positions, instead of adding to the matrix cell value (taken from $VMat(S)$) the maximum of two alternatives (the value from the left and the one from above), only the value from above is considered:

$$MSMat(S)_{p,m} = MSMat(S)_{p-1,m} + VMat(S)_{p,m}$$

As for the ordinary makespan calculation, the cells of the first row are computed slightly differently (since there is no row above):

- If the first position is *fixed*, as in the ordinary makespan calculation, the cells of the first row are filled with the value immediately to the left, added to the delay present at the same position in $Vmat(S)$:

$$MSMat(S)_{1,1} = VMat(S)_{1,1}$$

$$MSMat(S)_{1,m} = MSMat(S)_{1,m-1} + VMat(S)_{1,m}$$

- If the first position is *mobile*, then "negative infinity" is placed in all values of the first row except the first one (which simply contains the delay of the job in the first position for the first machine, taken from $Vmat(S)$).

$$MSMat(S)_{1,1} = VMat(S)_{1,1}$$

$$m > 1, MSMat(S)_{1,m} = -\infty$$

The compatibility makespan is the value obtained in the bottom-right matrix computation node (i.e., in column M and row P): $MSMat(S)_{P,M}$

This value is compared to the numerical limit L to determine if a schedule C is super-prohibited by a schedule S.

Remark: The super-prohibition relation is symmetric, and calculations can indifferently start from the $VMat(S)$ or $VMat(C)$ matrix.

We also note that if all positions are *mobile*, as in the case of the computation for (C_2, S) in Example 2 of paragraph E, the compatibility makespan is then negative infinity since $MSMat(S)_{P,M}$ is the sum of $-\infty$ and cells from the last column of $VMat$ (all except the one in the first row). This result is consistent with the fact that no path is common, for example, between a schedule and its reverse ordering.

Additional Remarks

No schedule whose makespan is lower than L is excluded by this super-prohibition condition, since any super-forbidden schedule must contain a path with a weight greater than L. This, however, is not a very useful guarantee, as the makespan is generally computed before the tabu list filtering step.

The space of admissible schedules is thus reduced locally, which prevents the algorithm from entering infinite loops and enables it to escape from local minima.

In comparison, one can think of heuristics that exclude certain jobs from certain ranks or make other cuts: but then, there is not always certainty about the makespan of the excluded schedules.

However, unlike the simple exclusion of schedules — which can be verified/implemented/accelerated using a hash table and a function that computes a checksum on each excluded schedule and then on the schedule whose exclusion we wish to test — the exclusion presented here requires specific computation for each pair $(C, S \in T)$. As a result, it is much more time-consuming for a given tabu list of orderings T.

But when seeking to solve a problem whose complexity is a priori above exponential, one does not rule out resorting to operations that do not alter the polynomial or non-polynomial

nature of the algorithm. One can even do whatever one wants with the product of the previous steps, provided it is done in polynomial time.

We know we will obtain an efficient algorithm for a given problem size, but less operational for larger problems.

The technique described above allows, at the cost of a computation "of complexity identical to that of a general/isolated makespan calculation" (i.e., without the factorizations proposed by Taillard for schedules forming an insertion neighborhood together), defining an exclusion zone sometimes very extensive around a set of tabu schedules.

To convince oneself of the extent of this tabu zone, it suffices to consider a path with weight greater than L having a vertical portion of 10 consecutive "mobile" ranks. For this single path, there are $10!$ schedules that will be excluded. And if other portions of this path are also vertical, this count must be multiplied by as many factorials.

Added to the fact that there may be many paths above the limit L (the best makespan reached at that moment), for a schedule S in the tabu list T , this creates a massive exclusion zone around T .

The exclusion zone is so extensive that the risk of trapping the global minimum of the problem (when it can no longer be reached because all its neighbors are super-forbidden) or the current schedule (when no non-super-forbidden neighbor can be found in the neighborhood) is very real, especially if one simply applies super-forbidden status in a "classic" local search engine with a tabu list.

The BRunner metaheuristic was designed around this basic building block, which produces quite a nice result for a relatively moderate cost.

Dynamic/Adaptive Neighborhood

The neighborhood is another important component of local searches, and thus of tabu methods.

It defines which solutions "close" to the "current position" are evaluated at each iteration, before one of them is selected. Its use can vary, particularly when the notion of current position becomes broader than a single schedule (for example, when performing nested local searches), but overall, there are always schedules considered near other schedules and a relationship between the former and the latter.

BRunner has several selectable neighborhoods in its startup configuration.

In this catalog of possibilities, I will only describe the most interesting neighborhood here. Interesting because it seems original to me (even though I have read little on the subject) and it allowed finding solutions where other neighborhoods had failed.

If someone has published this neighborhood before me, I apologize and ask them to share the reference so I can add it.

An isolated schedule makespan is usually computed in $P \times M$ steps.

The set of makespans for a neighborhood composed of "close" schedules, or having a form of structural proximity, can be computed faster than by multiplying the number of steps of a single computation by the cardinality of that neighborhood: Taillard presented such an optimization applicable to the insertion neighborhood.

We call a "mixer" a vector of P ranks (structurally identical to a schedule) used to shuffle the jobs of a base schedule to obtain a neighbor: the mixer is essentially an indirection table.

NBH-1: The swap of two consecutive jobs. There are P-1 neighbors of this type.

This neighborhood is not the "smallest" that reaches all possible schedule.

The circular shift of 1 rank, combined with the swap of jobs 1 and 2, already enables reaching the entire space of schedules with only 2 neighbors.

However, the best neighborhoods, for a given number of neighbors, are those that most reduce the number of local minima of the makespan function. A good arrangement of X very simple and "independent, even orthogonal" alternative neighborhoods is sometimes better than a single monolithic neighborhood extended to k-closure. It suffices that their local minima do not coincide for progress to be made by examining them all.

Without having succeeded in composing such a perfect set, we use the superposition of neighborhoods and call the different neighbor construction techniques "neighborhood compartments".

NBH-2 : Extraction of any job, followed by its reinsertion at another rank, without counting the swap of two consecutive jobs twice.

There are $(P-1)^2$ neighbors of this type, and this neighborhood contains NBH-1.

The Taillard90 technique allows computing the makespan of this entire neighborhood around a given base schedule relatively efficiently.

NBH-3 : A third neighborhood is the exchange of two distinct jobs.

There are $(P(P-1))/2$ neighbors in this neighborhood.

This neighborhood also contains all of NBH-1, and outside of NBH-1, it is completely disjoint from NBH-2.

One can observe that this neighborhood is entirely included in the 2-closure of the insertion neighborhood NBH-2 : NBH-3 is included in $NBH-2 \cup (NBH-2 \circ NBH-2)$

More precisely, its NBH-1 component is included in NBH-2, and the remainder is included in $(NBH-2 \circ NBH-2)$

NBH-3' : NBH-3' is NBH-3 excluding NBH-1, , i.e., all swaps of two non-contiguous jobs.

This compartment is to be added to a neighborhood that already includes NBH-1.

There are $(P(P-1))/2 - (P-1) = ((P-1)(P-2))/2$ neighbors in NBH-3'.

NBH-4 : This compartment adds to the previous compartments other neighbors included in the 2-closure of NBH-2, more precisely in $(NBH-2 \circ NBH-2)$.

It is an "adaptive" compartment because its mixers are not fixed:

- we start by computing the makespans of NBH-2 around the base schedule,
- then we select the P best NBH-2 neighbors and combine them with each other, rejecting neighbors already present in NBH-3 or Id (i.e., the mixer that changes no rank). This composition is performed thoughtfully.

For example, if one neighbor takes the job at rank 5 and inserts it at rank 12, and the other neighbor takes the job at rank 7 and inserts it at rank 2, the combination of the two neighbors:

- does not displace the job at rank 7 after the first move,
- takes the job that was originally at rank 7 and moves it to rank 2.

Defining such a neighbor from a combination of two mixers requires more advanced logic than simple indirect rank addressing.

By construction, NBH-4 is, like NBH-3, a subset of the 2-closure of NBH-2.

It is a selective partial 2-closure.

NBH-4 is not defined by a set of "fixed" mixers, unlike other neighborhoods, since it depends on the evaluation of NBH-2 neighbors.

The edge count in a clique with P vertices means there are $(P(P-1))/2$ neighbors in NBH-4.

Its size may vary slightly, as more or fewer mixer combinations from two NBH-2 mixers might already exist in NBH-3 or Id. In practice, when a combination is rejected, we simply generate more using lower-quality NBH-2 neighbors until each of the P best NBH-2 neighbors has its quota of accepted combinations.

There are therefore exactly $(P(P-1))/2$ neighbors in NBH-4.

We do not compute mixers "blindly" by composing NBH-2 mixers and then checking for duplicates in fixed neighborhoods. Instead, we analyze the abstract definition of the selected NBH-2 neighbors and avoid combining certain ones when they yield previously seen neighbors.

In BRunner, $NBH-11 = NBH-2 \cup NBH-3'$ and $NBH-15 = NBH-2 \cup NBH-3' \cup NBH-4$

This numbering of the compartmented neighborhoods is arbitrary.

NBH-11 was essentially used in versions 1 to 7 of this report.

NBH-15 is the "new neighborhood".

There are $(P-1)^2 + ((P-1)(P-2))/2 = ((P-1)(3P-4))/2$ neighbors in NBH-11

There are $(P-1)^2 + ((P-1)(P-2))/2 + (P(P-1))/2 = 2(P-1)^2$ neighbors in NBH-15, doubling NBH-2.

Jobs	Size of NBH-2 (insertion)	Size of NBH-11	Size of NBH-15
50	2401	3577	4802
60	3481	5192	6962
100	9801	14652	19602
200	39601	59302	79202
	1	≈ 1.5	2

For the computation of NBH-15, once the makespans of NBH-2 have been calculated using Taillard's optimization and the adaptive compartment NBH-4 has been defined, we proceed to compute the makespans of NBH-3' and NBH-4.

These two compartments share the trait that their makespans are computed independently for each neighbor, without any special optimization.

The computations for these two compartments are chained to fully leverage vectorized functions, which calculate up to 32 independent makespans per call.

While the use of NBH-15 has long seemed "superfluous" (it is often slower than NBH-11 on "easy" instances), the two runs are now systematically executed in parallel.

Quite often, especially in "difficult" cases, NBH-15 performs better: during the last improvement on Ta088, or during the re-runs performed to regain the lead on instances lost in version 8 of this report, it won hands down.

However, the NBH-11 run was still useful because it produced a known trace, allowing us to observe the speed gains from multi-threading and AVX512 compared to early 2025. There are still many instances with fewer than 100 jobs for which this neighborhood has not been used. Even though I currently have little time to devote to these researches, these runs will still be performed.

Perspectives :

NBH-15 exploits an NBH-4 of size $(P(P-1))/2$.

One advantage of NBH-4 is that its size can easily be modulated by adjusting the number of best NBH-2 neighbors considered. Thus the NBH-4 compartment can make NBH-15 vary from NBH-11 to the complete 2-closure of the insertion neighborhood.

Being able to dynamically vary a neighborhood's size is a capability that can prove useful if a metric and target value are available to control this parameter.

This is one of the future directions envisioned (although the list of other things to try first is quite long). It would enable combining, in a single adaptive run, the strengths of NBH-11 and NBH-15 runs.

Non-scalar makespan computations: multi-numbers

It is possible to represent any set of integers in a structure exploiting a base-one representation of them.

This structure is, in first approximation, a simple array of N numbers, each counting, at a given index, the number of times the index number is present in the set.

With this encoding of a set of numbers, instead of computing the maximum of two numbers at each step of a makespan calculation, we can merge two multi-numbers: add the cardinalities of the two multi-numbers for each index. The maximum can still be found by traversing the array from high indices until a non-zero cardinality is found, but these multi-numbers also provide, ultimately, information on the distribution of weights of all other possible paths in the delay matrix.

Adding a scalar to a multi-number is done by shifting the values in its array.

It is possible to rework the multi-number concept to achieve a representation that is no longer an array with fixed indices starting from 0, but a structure consisting of a maximum index value and an array of cardinalities for a limited range of lower values, starting from this maximum.

The limited precision of this representation — that is, the reduced size of its array part — makes it possible to handle multi-number makespans at low cost, while still containing more information than a single scalar makespan value.

Upper-windowing of multi-numbers can be applied throughout the computation of the multi-makespan, since only the *maximum of two multi-numbers* and the *addition of integers* need to be supported.

Having a multi-makespan allows comparing two schedules and breaking ties when their makespans (i.e., the highest value of the two multi-makespans) are equal: we can then select the schedule with fewer paths at the makespan weight, and if tied, descend through the values until a difference is found.

This criterion reflects a progressive version of the objective to reduce the makespan: "the fewer paths there are in the highest values, the closer we are to a makespan reduction".

This equivalence is not always verified, and counterexamples can be found, but using this criterion improves convergence.

This presentation is merely the remnant of a long experience with multi-numbers: A version with binary cardinalities (presence or absence) was mentioned in page 6 of [18], just before the state-of-the-art SVGA Windows 3.0 screen capture. Incidentally, the latter shows a spectrum of multi-numbers for the represented case with 20 jobs and 3 machines (not 20 machines like stated).

30 years later, the current implementation is therefore likely optimized beyond reason.

Earlier versions of my flowshop heuristics made broader use of these representations: using a geological analogy, when the "ground level" (i.e., makespan) no longer decreased around a schedule, the algorithm would try to find and follow deeper strata still exhibiting a slope, potentially escaping a local minimum relatively directly without a tabu list.

While the "duct tape theorem" does not truly exist for PFSP (there are no superimposed layers where the deepest inform surface trends), following deep layers still allows movement without abandoning an objectively improved state (stored in a multi-number), and "deciding on moves" even without foundation, until resurfacing to follow a surface slope.

Following any criterion not completely orthogonal to the main objective function sometimes suffices to escape a dead end. I had relatively successful results at the time with this technique, even if nothing could be shared.

Multi-numbers can be partially copied, or from a given rank, as if copying genes from chromosomes. More complex and progressive objectives than a scalar "Best MS found so far" can be constructed: a much more "improvable" state that's anti-cycling while remaining makespan-oriented at the margin.

These algorithms manipulated sets of numbers instead of a single one, exploiting information usually lost in projections $z = \max(x, y)$.

Finally, it is possible to abandon the array-based representation with indices by storing pairs (value, cardinality of that value), also truncating the multi-number to a high-end window of values. I programmed a class demonstrating this possibility, but the heuristic does not use it because it is less efficient on the targeted problem instances in these works.

These multi-numbers better address the plateaus encountered when multiple jobs have partially identical processing times.

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Results

Taillard Instances open / searched / improved: 12 / 11 / 6

100 jobs × 20 machines:

Ta081 (cost: 6171) improves 6173
54 78 59 74 79 3 1 83 51 4 60 40 6 33 81 22 35 76 28 63 18 86 21 82 99 12 10 44 85 5
16 70 56 65 80 61 71 9 53 25 30 93 62 32 100 42 55 91 48 41 46 73 11 31 89 50 96 37 39
29 67 92 15 77 47 95 23 20 87 45 17 34 2 66 64 24 90 72 68 88 52 19 43 58 57 36 38 84
14 98 26 94 27 69 7 49 13 75 97 8

Ta085 (cost : 6277) improves 6285
64 10 98 51 32 97 12 50 16 14 99 3 30 38 33 56 74 5 28 69 41 60 1 90 76 94 53 72 11 58
8 85 62 86 2 46 20 9 49 52 45 31 21 95 39 61 70 71 22 18 88 37 87 65 36 6 17 81 27 96
55 92 23 4 40 82 26 68 57 63 25 66 29 93 54 15 35 34 59 80 13 100 48 89 84 24 75 42 77
79 73 44 91 67 7 43 19 47 83 78

Ta086 (cost: 6329) improves 6331
83 32 2 12 21 33 39 92 37 69 1 86 31 82 88 89 60 7 56 28 55 34 81 99 23 72 38 14 65 52
97 66 75 8 98 94 40 80 71 10 57 20 100 18 48 16 45 58 78 91 76 25 49 27 22 35 15 6 63
84 95 68 9 26 77 53 17 54 74 13 64 44 79 24 61 87 50 41 5 36 85 43 4 67 19 73 62 70 46
3 30 29 93 11 51 59 47 96 42 90

Ta087 (cost: 6221) improves 6223
93 85 62 96 95 67 94 32 23 27 88 60 49 64 57 28 39 48 89 45 16 66 6 43 54 24 59 97 73
19 29 21 84 69 82 20 40 58 91 13 34 42 8 51 36 55 31 72 17 38 98 79 4 9 14 12 78 47 18
77 87 22 33 71 100 53 41 92 99 3 30 65 7 46 90 63 37 2 11 61 26 74 70 80 10 5 50 52 81
56 35 25 1 15 44 83 68 86 76 75

Ta088 (cost: 6357) improves 6372
39 62 29 90 73 22 87 70 7 64 69 31 36 71 59 72 9 45 3 5 78 14 44 56 67 88 12 58 17 91
81 68 25 57 28 27 32 41 83 24 98 53 23 18 40 37 49 51 1 80 76 19 30 100 93 54 94 95 48
4 10 50 74 55 66 16 47 85 43 89 52 84 33 77 35 38 6 82 2 8 63 75 26 86 34 21 65 42 60
79 99 61 11 96 46 92 13 15 97 20

Ta089 (cost: 6246) improves 6247
47 2 7 80 60 41 94 50 15 90 43 81 63 42 95 68 51 78 21 74 17 10 79 62 97 34 19 65 4 38
57 77 83 12 16 20 61 59 30 1 96 89 86 92 25 26 23 33 54 45 39 46 24 82 84 3 13 71 32
11 40 8 70 55 49 100 53 18 73 99 87 48 14 56 69 36 37 58 27 6 93 72 31 64 85 52 9 67
44 35 29 76 88 28 22 5 91 75 66 98

Improved Vallada, Ruiz & Framinan instances

"Small" instances open / searched / improved: 39 / 39 / 16

VFR40_15_10 (lmin47s - cost: 2940) improves 2943
29 14 28 40 1 18 16 6 12 13 21 35 19 30 34 10 36 11 2 27 38 33 8 17 5 37 4 32 31 9 20
39 23 25 26 3 15 22 7 24

VFR50_15_10 (15min57s - cost : 3394) improves 3396
16 27 31 14 1 10 40 35 49 33 5 6 7 13 3 39 20 9 23 21 12 4 37 8 28 50 47 36 29 46 48
38 25 34 11 18 30 43 15 42 2 32 41 22 45 24 26 17 44 19

VFR50_20_2 (9min - cost: 3698) improves 3707
15 4 19 13 25 6 8 39 27 40 20 41 35 5 45 9 29 44 48 17 24 2 33 49 1 14 7 34 30 16 23
47 31 21 22 26 11 12 42 3 38 10 50 28 18 46 32 37 43 36

VFR50_20_4 (7min22s - cost: 3700) improves 3702
26 12 16 48 5 38 41 17 22 29 24 18 36 35 19 23 11 43 14 28 13 21 49 4 46 10 1 37 34 45
3 33 31 32 7 20 47 42 25 6 9 8 40 44 50 30 27 2 39 15

VFR50_20_8 (29min22s - cost: 3770) improves 3771
16 34 5 19 7 26 15 37 36 33 23 21 20 43 41 14 46 2 18 22 9 50 39 44 49 10 42 47 45 4
11 32 12 31 38 48 40 8 3 1 6 17 28 13 25 29 35 24 27 30

VFR50_20_9 (3h28min - cost: 3797) improves 3799
10 17 43 48 42 9 1 37 3 7 15 26 23 27 24 46 41 49 31 18 38 25 32 40 14 21 35 4 47 8 44
22 6 13 33 29 11 36 45 50 2 39 19 12 34 30 28 20 5 16

VFR60_20_1 (1h32min - cost: 4146) improves 4147
50 53 25 41 49 8 30 40 28 21 45 18 57 59 9 26 10 58 52 7 1 54 22 16 4 34 13 24 35 3 46
29 20 43 48 32 37 51 39 42 47 19 14 2 31 12 17 33 56 55 6 11 5 38 36 15 27 23 60 44

VFR60_20_2 (2h26min - cost: 4257) improves 4274 (-0.4 %) - 4273 en 2min4s
48 8 50 16 56 40 43 19 2 29 28 5 52 24 31 20 57 9 45 18 4 3 35 11 25 26 42 34 39 30 47
36 58 44 1 49 46 27 17 33 37 13 7 51 12 60 21 41 59 55 23 15 6 38 14 10 32 22 54 53

VFR60_20_3 (21h50min - cost: 4332) improves 4341
45 20 6 28 60 12 32 22 19 29 7 23 27 2 44 24 40 53 36 58 17 3 43 39 31 1 47 48 8 59 33
35 50 21 16 42 9 18 56 34 10 55 38 15 5 57 14 41 25 51 37 26 13 30 11 49 54 52 4 46

VFR60_20_4 (2h40min - cost: 4168) improves 4175
39 2 40 30 12 16 58 28 29 10 26 25 7 3 45 56 13 55 27 24 4 18 50 19 15 6 9 49 33 44 53
5 47 42 48 1 54 20 22 60 59 32 23 46 37 17 41 43 14 35 31 57 21 52 8 36 38 51 11 34

VFR60_20_5 (18h11min38s - cost: 4172) improves 4173
37 56 19 47 32 41 31 21 29 12 22 25 5 51 46 40 24 50 16 11 26 18 44 60 43 55 17 58 23
3 35 9 13 20 45 15 33 2 7 1 10 27 28 8 57 54 36 49 4 59 53 48 14 6 39 42 30 34 38 52

VFR60_20_6 (1h33min - cost: 4173) improves 4184
35 40 37 14 1 43 33 11 41 13 20 57 47 21 51 18 55 16 2 36 46 60 26 48 4 29 54 59 52 5
24 25 15 56 10 31 3 39 30 50 32 44 27 6 7 28 17 53 42 8 23 22 9 45 34 38 12 58 49 19

VFR60_20_7 (41min28s - cost: 4245) improves 4251
41 42 46 18 55 33 5 25 6 3 23 7 53 20 48 58 52 11 37 40 13 24 2 19 60 59 35 1 49 57 21
45 32 38 27 8 47 50 44 26 29 56 4 14 39 43 36 28 22 31 10 30 16 17 34 15 54 12 51 9

VFR60_20_8 (4h30min - cost: 4166) improves 4171
4 9 45 35 31 17 13 30 15 43 10 23 57 47 16 50 56 55 6 2 29 14 37 7 24 19 21 53 41 12 3
60 39 44 28 54 27 32 42 25 8 38 52 40 48 20 18 59 11 34 51 26 46 58 1 33 49 36 22 5

VFR60_20_9 (3h25min - cost: 4192) improves 4198
55 19 41 56 49 15 28 59 44 29 52 11 12 37 42 40 7 34 53 33 17 24 13 4 20 5 22 46 54 25
35 1 51 26 27 57 8 6 21 18 3 10 9 47 23 2 16 48 58 32 45 43 39 30 60 14 38 36 50 31

VFR60_20_10 (1h14min - cost: 4173) improves 4186
20 42 5 53 25 50 30 49 41 4 46 15 34 10 22 47 56 51 19 35 11 43 45 39 12 37 17 33 7 44
60 58 32 8 21 55 9 54 27 57 3 59 29 2 38 13 36 28 24 16 48 6 52 40 14 1 18 26 23 31

"Large" instances open / searched / improved (work in progress): 175 / 30 / 30

VFR100_20_1 (88h44min - cost: 6116) improves 6221
86 39 52 100 34 14 97 11 36 61 62 58 22 81 9 18 48 32 77 29 68 44 95 83 21 28 27 72 17
42 20 25 64 53 90 24 37 65 70 93 78 12 69 43 59 55 6 96 5 56 87 82 84 75 1 91 63 76 7
31 45 60 67 4 46 35 41 2 92 50 98 88 13 57 40 49 94 26 85 66 54 16 51 23 80 19 89 10
99 30 71 8 15 74 33 79 73 3 47 38

VFR100_20_2 (151h6min - cost: 6217) improves 6224
92 52 7 66 17 16 79 95 34 96 45 86 61 12 15 5 97 42 41 26 21 14 28 9 84 22 60 49 25 94
57 88 3 8 70 37 38 10 27 87 44 67 78 89 68 72 32 30 69 55 71 43 11 93 65 35 4 82 77 54
100 2 75 98 20 91 81 58 29 76 6 62 31 74 63 46 56 19 90 73 50 24 51 80 59 53 48 40 39
85 1 83 33 47 23 99 13 18 36 64

VFR100_20_3 (37h45min - cost : 6147) improves 6157
10 58 59 34 53 78 73 13 50 16 39 11 19 64 75 41 91 26 25 93 86 43 67 29 17 80 100 71
55 47 37 81 72 38 61 12 62 33 88 23 46 21 6 95 45 42 35 3 92 99 15 69 49 65 9 79 40 14
98 85 22 87 20 24 1 7 74 84 8 48 44 36 77 4 97 2 51 18 94 83 5 66 70 76 31 68 89 27 82
54 56 32 63 28 60 52 30 96 90 57

VFR100_20_4 (63h6min - cost: 6167) improves 6173
68 66 95 36 83 47 54 88 17 40 32 35 15 49 21 2 94 99 52 20 12 27 51 18 25 11 8 41 90
77 31 5 62 1 30 72 97 79 70 98 82 76 86 71 4 58 9 75 87 63 84 34 29 43 65 57 7 85 55
74 24 67 53 3 60 13 16 80 26 81 91 61 19 92 37 100 44 22 14 93 42 89 28 56 48 73 23 10
59 46 39 6 33 50 38 64 45 96 69 78

VFR100_20_5 (55h46min - cost: 6210) improves 6221
2 61 92 89 16 26 71 42 50 12 18 41 94 27 79 30 52 99 87 11 8 34 17 15 97 40 90 10 29
72 6 100 91 75 55 7 22 23 14 47 25 70 86 57 74 88 68 37 39 83 44 51 69 28 82 3 93 24
96 49 5 19 59 33 4 1 45 67 85 64 54 95 58 81 13 20 62 36 35 46 9 48 78 21 60 63 66 76
56 43 77 98 32 31 38 53 65 73 84 80

VFR100_20_6 (4h32min - cost: 6240) improves 6247
10 40 82 7 95 26 24 8 73 9 4 84 62 47 41 17 37 70 35 49 97 85 74 81 15 58 94 56 66 69
61 93 12 20 91 60 18 27 42 19 68 46 23 43 90 25 34 50 48 75 45 67 59 52 71 53 55 32 11
33 30 64 6 57 22 77 76 89 80 54 72 83 31 29 13 36 98 79 1 51 92 5 88 28 65 2 96 87 21
99 3 78 14 63 44 100 16 86 38 39

VFR100_20_7 (73h23min - cost: 6354) improves 6358
8 20 57 9 3 70 58 56 82 2 78 47 19 41 83 17 28 51 50 45 99 30 98 88 22 46 61 73 68 10
87 85 16 92 7 71 53 11 34 29 64 39 69 97 54 55 93 94 84 5 90 18 76 100 96 4 79 62 80
37 13 65 86 67 36 43 66 40 59 25 12 60 44 15 95 23 72 42 31 77 49 74 27 1 14 75 35 24
33 63 6 48 91 38 21 52 26 81 32 89

VFR100_20_8 (154h37min - cost: 6016) improves 6023
1 18 23 70 2 74 56 61 44 12 11 27 94 16 91 9 37 97 31 28 83 72 17 8 4 66 52 33 49 32 5
69 68 54 24 47 92 25 85 50 99 41 71 95 21 58 3 53 73 87 93 89 7 78 20 42 29 51 43 55
46 10 86 26 30 48 19 67 90 40 13 15 100 59 34 84 75 79 64 62 82 98 45 35 14 96 65 60
81 57 38 39 77 63 80 88 6 22 76 36

VFR100_20_9 (73h44min - cost: 6274) improves 6286
73 34 90 33 36 82 46 57 3 89 14 94 26 7 21 6 69 72 27 30 23 76 5 100 40 99 51 43 93 70
77 18 50 91 29 55 44 87 92 60 88 79 37 65 12 39 16 80 59 19 54 97 78 35 41 28 75 68 49
45 52 31 61 66 2 74 62 17 47 9 63 15 56 20 67 8 71 22 24 38 11 32 42 86 1 96 4 48 85
64 81 98 83 10 84 58 25 13 95 53

VFR100_20_10 (40h - cost : 6075) improves 6084
20 30 98 6 60 24 7 23 39 35 36 63 62 22 79 58 72 66 54 51 71 65 17 25 44 10 29 15 75
38 82 21 89 70 77 1 76 95 19 55 12 50 16 78 69 53 45 86 47 32 74 85 80 94 96 67 11 3
64 99 46 100 61 97 56 91 37 87 13 73 48 59 33 8 27 81 9 2 49 26 83 4 57 42 93 68 90 88
5 18 28 14 84 40 31 34 41 52 92 43

VFR100_40_1 (50h49min - cost: 7783) improves 7933 (-1.89 %)
78 11 20 13 3 15 75 6 24 74 35 10 60 53 91 27 21 34 14 72 96 61 38 30 57 23 99 2 73 28
87 59 83 22 4 49 43 25 7 41 46 62 51 86 44 98 29 80 9 85 54 37 5 1 65 77 95 97 81 40
94 89 90 18 93 92 42 64 69 66 63 19 16 17 36 45 39 56 52 100 31 88 26 58 55 32 76 68
12 47 70 67 8 82 33 50 48 71 84 79

VFR100_40_2 (18h44min - cost: 7905) improves 8004 (-1.24 %)
9 52 16 35 3 50 39 80 88 92 58 29 85 55 22 67 79 51 48 78 72 20 81 19 6 57 37 47 27 1
70 44 40 4 69 11 82 41 68 24 95 91 10 56 49 28 31 26 61 36 23 18 42 99 5 97 60 94 89
59 62 53 17 43 63 74 38 54 64 45 30 84 2 8 14 21 77 25 75 93 7 76 73 65 15 83 32 100
86 33 71 98 13 96 34 12 66 87 46 90

VFR100_40_3 (39h11min - cost: 7838) improves 7909 (-0.90 %)
78 81 63 22 65 64 28 25 6 73 69 59 68 61 44 82 37 60 45 39 86 58 26 7 38 92 51 89 76
62 56 98 49 1 88 27 70 9 99 53 93 90 14 95 36 71 15 33 100 21 80 10 83 43 24 87 19 84
67 42 41 50 11 34 16 35 47 23 91 5 46 97 13 75 4 85 17 3 72 79 30 32 48 12 20 52 29 96
57 55 18 31 77 2 8 74 66 94 40 54

VFR100_40_4 (11h20min - cost: 7866) improves 7942 (-0.96 %)
38 42 91 27 75 18 90 99 62 93 16 97 33 94 7 44 61 22 2 5 83 34 55 48 50 59 64 30 49 1
85 87 14 21 29 17 78 20 12 43 41 67 89 52 72 31 57 100 26 10 92 70 4 39 86 96 32 13 65
28 11 15 37 51 3 45 23 77 19 80 6 84 36 53 71 56 54 9 95 88 81 74 73 47 58 60 66 8 24
79 63 76 25 82 68 98 69 40 35 46

VFR100_40_5 (14h45min - cost: 7916) improves 8004 (-1.10 %)
78 71 89 80 31 72 4 47 76 43 41 7 66 36 10 62 1 6 77 82 29 60 13 27 69 56 81 54 17 35
55 24 92 25 20 45 28 16 19 95 79 65 38 58 75 42 2 67 61 50 52 37 51 33 94 49 39 15 40
12 73 26 9 74 34 5 18 91 46 59 100 97 96 53 44 14 85 3 8 90 98 11 63 68 84 83 22 99 88
57 93 30 64 86 48 70 21 32 87 23

VFR100_40_6 (92h17min - cost: 7927) improves 8017 (-1.12 %)
15 10 59 29 65 37 93 20 86 8 92 36 16 47 72 88 33 40 80 28 82 98 63 18 22 99 71 77 24
89 34 74 51 90 79 83 62 66 9 1 6 54 56 57 35 3 58 87 32 26 55 48 7 75 13 70 96 78 30
60 64 11 76 52 21 69 25 53 31 44 19 84 38 97 85 49 14 91 4 5 100 43 27 94 45 67 17 42
73 61 68 12 50 95 81 46 39 2 23 41

VFR100_40_7 (9h38min - cost: 7912) improves 7996 (-1.05 %)
20 98 96 83 80 15 12 36 99 76 14 2 72 49 54 3 57 13 37 28 1 69 94 48 70 45 39 23 59 67
91 6 86 73 52 11 22 62 71 88 85 95 30 27 74 79 87 9 93 25 10 77 51 82 55 100 81 24 63
58 56 5 32 17 16 78 65 18 46 47 41 89 64 84 21 43 31 42 50 75 33 26 97 38 68 7 34 61
53 90 4 44 8 40 19 29 92 60 66 35

VFR100_40_8 (64h45min - cost: 7883) improves 7960 (-0.97 %)
84 5 97 9 62 25 55 27 37 16 86 59 19 32 10 46 64 56 51 20 24 28 15 6 60 87 21 61 80 3
75 43 1 89 23 65 95 12 77 48 52 18 49 82 100 83 42 58 68 53 63 14 17 7 90 74 85 40 92
45 66 50 54 4 76 88 30 35 36 31 29 93 47 34 72 38 98 22 67 8 70 71 2 41 33 26 79 91 73
94 78 44 11 39 57 13 99 96 81 69

VFR100_40_9 (24h7min - cost: 7834) improves 7901 (-0.85 %)
35 55 39 72 64 43 13 19 16 6 8 96 49 93 23 33 22 68 27 58 30 62 9 76 67 17 59 65 78 25
26 52 47 54 40 98 79 7 81 38 20 69 75 37 51 57 56 32 90 61 18 85 28 45 5 50 86 94 84
21 36 83 11 15 2 29 53 66 73 12 46 14 77 42 44 91 10 100 41 99 70 80 31 63 60 3 74 24
71 1 48 92 88 4 82 97 89 87 34 95

VFR100_40_10 (99h16min - cost: 7841) improves 7939 (-1.23 %)
75 69 18 23 28 52 83 9 73 53 74 59 33 64 67 21 57 77 82 8 24 39 12 10 97 95 36 93 87
32 43 55 44 96 63 66 45 62 13 26 76 56 80 98 61 40 25 81 41 34 22 37 50 90 78 72 68 35
7 30 79 16 42 38 17 46 100 71 60 15 5 58 47 92 94 6 65 3 11 54 29 88 19 85 89 4 84 70
99 20 14 49 86 1 48 51 27 91 2 31

VFR100_60_1 (21h40min - cost: 9287) improves 9353 (-0.71 %)
24 100 79 4 42 2 55 62 82 59 64 45 52 96 3 48 77 71 43 94 58 5 21 12 9 7 13 25 80 38
22 6 34 28 41 98 30 89 44 56 16 10 63 65 61 99 78 11 92 37 17 31 74 14 60 54 90 46 26
93 50 18 73 67 88 23 29 40 84 36 53 83 70 69 57 33 97 1 95 8 20 81 35 27 68 39 15 19
72 85 32 91 66 51 76 47 87 49 75 86

VFR100_60_2 (105h41min - cost: 9493) improves 9567 (-0.77 %)
97 95 89 42 46 56 64 94 31 10 98 72 65 28 40 9 96 19 18 71 78 12 43 85 69 32 3 83 61
63 48 13 47 60 51 35 1 8 68 41 55 34 84 59 14 29 44 80 76 20 16 86 74 27 45 49 79 57
52 100 37 70 67 17 7 91 39 6 5 2 22 87 77 81 36 15 92 50 30 54 62 38 33 11 99 24 90 75
93 82 66 58 73 25 26 53 23 4 88 21

VFR100_60_3 (71h15min - cost: 9270) improves 9349 (-0.85 %)
97 95 89 42 46 56 64 94 31 10 98 72 65 28 40 9 96 19 18 71 78 12 69 63 61 35 3 13 43
47 83 48 32 60 51 34 84 8 1 68 41 55 37 59 14 29 44 80 76 20 16 86 85 74 27 45 49 79
57 15 52 100 70 67 17 7 91 39 6 5 2 22 87 77 81 36 92 50 30 54 62 38 33 11 99 24 90 75
93 82 66 58 73 25 26 53 23 4 88 21

VFR100_60_4 (2h2min - cost: 9330) improves 9403 (-0.78 %)
52 61 55 21 6 74 16 67 94 73 79 4 77 5 34 31 68 82 69 23 46 17 39 60 25 75 18 51 96 70
20 42 12 56 87 13 38 8 41 81 28 32 2 92 45 65 98 10 97 7 84 91 29 58 30 88 78 3 19 36
49 85 43 59 48 80 93 14 37 11 44 76 71 9 26 1 57 24 40 95 53 99 86 27 15 90 72 83 54
63 100 89 33 35 22 62 66 64 47 50

VFR100_60_5 (57h41min - cost : 9345) improves 9369
18 53 72 38 28 11 84 46 77 92 64 62 4 14 82 78 70 49 65 85 2 57 41 91 51 8 83 24 86 44
16 88 75 19 40 45 37 48 39 29 96 34 56 23 73 52 54 27 9 74 93 47 69 6 59 90 81 7 31 63
12 33 32 25 100 50 15 20 95 3 68 55 61 17 76 79 99 42 71 26 10 43 30 66 94 67 87 21 35
13 98 1 60 97 89 58 5 36 80 22

VFR100_60_6 (42h6min - cost: 9576) improves 9630 (-0.56 %)
94 44 76 61 84 46 33 4 9 48 28 23 50 87 1 19 31 36 100 78 88 95 43 14 16 18 80 99 10
57 20 17 97 96 65 47 82 54 55 39 89 98 69 67 34 13 90 56 49 53 51 63 68 5 71 26 35 22
64 60 41 86 83 52 92 40 72 32 62 27 30 81 7 75 91 3 11 38 59 29 15 12 70 73 79 24 25
37 42 58 85 6 2 74 21 77 8 93 45 66

VFR100_60_7 (22h36min - cost: 9299) improves 9346 (-0.50 %)
41 65 5 86 39 29 46 72 59 100 96 95 61 18 12 76 10 54 92 67 45 36 27 97 79 32 60 64 58
48 50 15 21 53 31 81 26 19 34 17 28 57 47 22 44 3 94 71 35 89 49 85 90 56 7 91 43 14 6
84 16 51 13 55 99 68 11 9 37 69 42 23 52 40 30 8 20 33 93 80 74 88 66 2 24 98 63 70 82
1 62 73 25 77 87 75 4 78 38 83

VFR100_60_8 (31h33min - cost: 9454) improves 9523 (-0.72 %)
57 74 71 27 99 39 66 88 59 44 84 56 6 93 10 79 41 13 58 65 20 51 40 64 9 15 89 16 90
21 4 42 97 75 81 25 76 34 92 29 7 67 45 50 54 23 12 36 98 60 28 35 26 30 52 91 70 94
55 38 49 19 17 80 100 63 85 96 72 82 31 5 46 18 22 43 32 53 47 8 24 69 73 77 68 61 11
62 33 87 14 48 3 37 78 2 1 86 83 95

VFR100_60_9 (178h30min - cost: 9416) improves 9445 (-0.31 %)
94 73 42 20 87 96 66 25 11 18 38 92 40 68 62 5 44 84 39 100 52 6 35 63 71 21 16 7 57
41 82 48 46 99 88 59 51 77 27 10 47 37 81 91 60 24 33 13 61 2 67 65 50 14 54 64 79 55
26 45 70 97 34 83 95 72 98 3 1 53 23 32 78 86 9 43 36 58 89 17 22 30 56 15 75 31 49 19
8 80 4 76 29 12 74 28 69 93 85 90

VFR100_60_10 (111h51min - cost: 9499) improves 9572 (-0.76 %)
70 82 88 78 20 31 73 8 29 21 92 3 58 9 87 49 6 28 19 66 41 18 50 10 57 61 97 4 22 80
99 36 68 72 14 13 94 48 59 46 26 76 96 37 95 90 56 75 64 84 63 7 85 60 62 24 83 91 55
39 86 71 67 45 33 51 34 42 27 11 32 43 77 23 81 79 15 54 74 12 16 47 44 53 98 52 35 1
2 69 40 65 30 38 100 17 25 5 93 89